

PREVALENCE OF MENOPAUSAL SYMPTOMS AND THEIR IMPACT ON QUALITY OF LIFE AMONG POSTMENOPAUSAL WOMEN IN A TERTIARY CARE CENTER IN KERALA

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ABSTRACT

Background: Menopause is a natural physiological transition characterized by the cessation of menstruation for 12 consecutive months. This phase is frequently accompanied by physical, psychological, and emotional symptoms that may negatively affect a woman's quality of life (QOL). Understanding the prevalence and impact of these symptoms is crucial for designing appropriate health interventions. **Objectives:** To determine the prevalence of postmenopausal symptoms and assess their impact on the quality of life among postmenopausal women attending a tertiary care centre. **Materials and Methods:** A hospital-based cross-sectional study was conducted in the outpatient and inpatient departments of a tertiary care centre in Palakkad from 1st June 2024 to 1st August 2024. A total of 127 postmenopausal women aged 45–60 years who consented to participate were included. Women with induced menopause, those on hormonal therapy, with chronic medical conditions such as thyroid disorders, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, or unwilling to participate were excluded. Data were collected using the Menopause-Specific Quality of Life (MENQOL) questionnaire. **Results:** 'Willingness to be alone' (87.40%), a psychosocial domain symptom, was the most prevalent. Among the four MENQOL domains, the physical domain recorded the highest mean score (23.35 ± 17.86), indicating symptoms such as fatigue, joint pain, and sleep disturbances. Overall, 73% had a good QOL, 26% moderate, and 1% poor. QOL showed a significant association with education (p=0.006), socioeconomic status (p=0.003), and postmenopausal duration (p=0.002). **Conclusion:** Most postmenopausal women reported good QOL. Education, socioeconomic status, and longer postmenopausal duration were key determinants of better QOL. Targeted health education and psychosocial support may further enhance well-being.

KEYWORDS: Menopause, Postmenopausal symptoms, Quality of life, MENQOL, Kerala, Women's health.

INTRODUCTION

As per the World Health Organization (WHO) report, menopause is defined as 12 months of amenorrhea in women. More than 25 million women reached menopause in worldwide in the 1990 and it would be increase in double by the year 2020 and above years.^[1]

Menopause is the common physiological change among middleaged women. Menopausal health demands priority in India due to extension in the life expectancy and growing population of menopausal women.^[2]The

transition from the reproductive to the nonreproductive stage is the result of a reduction in the female hormonal production by the ovaries.

This transition is normally not sudden or abrupt; it tends to occur over a period of years; it is normally occurring in the aging of women's life and mostly occurring in the developed countries. Postmenopause describes the period following the final menses.

Quality of life (QOL) has been defined by the WHO as “the individual perception of their position in life in the context of the cultural and value systems in which they live and in relation to their goals, expectation, standards and concerns.”^[3]

The main objectives of our study were to assess the QOL among postmenopausal women and to find the association between QOL with demographic variables.

OBJECTIVES

1. To estimate the prevalence of postmenopausal symptoms among menopausal women of Kerala.
3. To assess the QOL among postmenopausal women.
2. To find the association between QOL with selected demographic variables.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present study was conducted in a tertiary care hospital and was designed as a hospital-based cross-sectional study. The study was carried out over a period of two months, from 1st June 2024 to 1st August 2024. The study population consisted of postmenopausal women attending various outpatient departments of the tertiary care centre. Postmenopausal status was defined as cessation of menstruation for at least twelve consecutive months without any other physiological or pathological cause.

All women who had attained natural menopause for more than one year and who were willing to participate were included in the study. Women with unnatural menopause, such as those who had undergone surgical removal of ovaries or received radiotherapy for carcinoma cervix, were excluded. Those who were taking medications such as anxiolytics or antidepressants, which could influence mood or bias psychological symptom reporting, were also excluded. Women with serious systemic illnesses such as thyroid disorders, those with mental retardation, cognitive impairment, or psychiatric illness, and those too ill to respond or with communication difficulties were excluded from participation. Women who did not provide consent or were unwilling to take part at any stage of the study were also excluded. A convenient sampling technique was used for participant selection. Eligible postmenopausal women attending the hospital during the study period were approached and included until the required sample size was achieved. The sample size was calculated based on a previous study conducted by Senthilvel et al. (2012)^[4], which reported a prevalence of menopausal symptoms of 54.6% at a 95% confidence level and a relative precision of 20%. Using the formula $N = 4pq/d^2$, where $p = 54.6$, $q = 100 - p = 45.4$, and $d = 20\%$ of $p = 10.92$, the calculated sample size was 102. On adding non-response rate of 10%, data was collected from 127 participants.

Data were collected using a semi-structured questionnaire, which consisted of two parts:

1. Socio-demographic profile: This section included details such as age, education, occupation, marital status, family type, and socioeconomic status. The socioeconomic status was assessed using the Modified BG Prasad's Classification.

2. Menopause-Specific Quality of Life (MENQOL) Questionnaire.

The MENQOL questionnaire is a standardized and validated instrument specifically designed to assess the quality of life among postmenopausal women.

It contains 29 items grouped under four domains: vasomotor symptoms (3 items), psychosocial symptoms (7 items), physical symptoms (16 items), and sexual symptoms (3 items). Each item follows a 6-point Likert scale, where the participant indicates whether she has experienced the symptom in the past six months, and if so, rates the degree of bother from 0 (not at all bothered) to 6 (extremely bothered).

The domain scores were calculated separately, and a composite MENQOL score was derived to reflect the overall quality of life. Higher scores indicated greater botheration and poorer quality of life.

Before the commencement of data collection, approval was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee and the Scientific Committee of the institution. Informed written consent was obtained from each participant after explaining the purpose and nature of the study. Data collection was conducted through face-to-face interviews using the structured MENQOL questionnaire, ensuring privacy and confidentiality. Each interview was conducted in a language familiar to the participant to facilitate understanding and accurate responses.

The collected data were entered and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20.0. Descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation, frequencies, and percentages were used to summarize the data. Fisher's test was applied to determine associations between menopausal symptoms and selected sociodemographic variables such as age, education, and socioeconomic status. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Table 1: Distribution of socioeconomic characteristics among postmenopausal women (N= 127)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Age groups (years)		
45 ≤ 55	68	53.5
56 -65	59	46.5
Religion		
Hindu	66	52
Muslim	60	47
Christian	1	1%
Education		
Illiterate	11	8.7
Primary school (1st to 5th standard)	32	25.2
Middle school (5th to 8 standard)	31	24.4
High School (8 to 10 th standard)	41	32.3
Graduate or above	4	3.1
Type of family		
Joint	14	11.0
Nuclear	97	76.4
Three generation	16	12.6
Socio Economic Status according to modified B.G Prasad Scale		
Upper Class (Class 1)	27	21.3
Upper Middle (Class 2)	27	21.3
Lower Middle (Class 3)	26	20.5
Upper Lower (Class 4)	34	26.8
Lower (Class 5)	13	10.2
Physical Activity		
Sedentary	23	18.1
Moderate	85	66.9
Heavy	19	15.0
History of chronic illness		
Yes	77	60.6
No	50	39.4
Postmenopausal stage		
≤7 Years	68	53.5
> 7 Years	59	46.5

Table 2: Distribution of study subjects according to menopausal symptoms.

Menopausal symptoms*	Number of postmenopausal women (%)
Vasomotor symptoms	
Hot flushes or flashes	58(45.67%)
Night sweats	60(72.24%)
Sweating	63(49.6%)
Psychosocial symptoms	
Dissatisfaction with my personal life	23(18.11%)
Feeling anxious or nervous	49(38.58%)
Poor memory	44(34.65%)
Accomplishing less than I used to	88(69.29%)
Feeling depressed, down or blue	32(25.10%)
Impatience with other people	49(38.58%)
Willing to be alone	111(87.04%)
Physical symptoms	
Flatulence	56(44.09%)
Aching in muscles and joints	81(63.78%)
Feeling tired or worn out	89(70.07%)
Difficulty in sleeping	53(41.73%)
Aches in back of neck or head	50(39.37%)
Decrease in physical strength	108(85.03%)

Decrease in stamina (energy to keep going)	108(85.03%)
Feeling Lack of energy	102(80.31%)
Drying skin	23(18.11%)
Facial hair	6(4.72%)
Weight gain	27(21.26%)
Changes in appearance, texture or tone of your skin	19(14.96%)
Feeling bloated	41(32.28%)
Low backache	60(47.24%)
Frequent urination	34(26.77%)
Involuntary urination when laughing or coughing	32(25.19%)
Sexual Symptoms	
Changes in sexual desire	19(14.96%)
Vaginal dryness during intercourse	24(18.89%)
Avoiding intimacy	28(22.04%)

*Multiple responses

Fig-1: Distribution of Quality of life among post menopausal women according to MENQOL Score (N=127)

Figure 1 depicts the distribution of quality of life among postmenopausal women. The majority of participants reported a good quality of life, followed by a smaller

proportion with moderate quality of life, while only a minimal number experienced a poor quality of life.

Table 3: Association Between Quality Of Life And Sociodemographic Variables (N= 127).

Variables	Quality of Life			Total No (%)	Fishers exact test	P value
	Good Quality of life	Moderate Quality of life	Poor Quality of life			
Age						
45 - 55	49 (72.1%)	18 (26.5%)	1 (1.5%)	68 (100%)	0.859	1.000
56 - 60	44 (74.6%)	15 (25.4%)	1(0%)	59 (100%)		
Education						
Illiterate	2(18.2%)	5(45.5%)	4(36.4%)	11(100%)	23.868	0.006***
Primary school	23(71.9%)	9(28.1%)	0(0.0%)	32(100%)		
Middle school	27(87.1%)	4 (12.9%)	0(0.0%)	31(100%)		
High School	28 (68.1%)	13(31.7%)	0(0.0%)	41(100%)		
Predegree or diploma	8(62.5%)	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	8(100%)		
Graduate or above	3(75%)	0(0.0%)	1(25%)	4(100%)		
Type of family						
Nuclear	67 (69.1%)	29 (29.9%)	1(1.0%)	97	5.079	0.360

				(100.0%)		
Joint	13(92.9%)	1(7.1%)	0(0.0%)	14 (100.0%)		
Three generation	13 (81.2%)	3 (18.8%)	0 (0.0%)	16 (100.0%)		
EMPLOYMENT STATUS						
Employed	26(78.8%)	6(18.2%)	1(3.0%)	33 (1000%)	3.638	0.139
Not Employed	67(71.3%)	27(28.7%)	0(0.0%)	94(100.0%)		
SOCIO ECONOMIC STATUS ACCORDING TO MODIFIED B.G PRASAD SCALE						
Class 1	26 (96.3%)	1 (3.7%)	0 (0.0%)	27 (100.0%)	19.280	0.003***
Class 2	16(59.3%)	10 (37.0%)	1(3.7%)	27 (100.0%)		
Class 3	21(80.8%)	5(19.2%)	9(0.0%)	26 (100.0%)		
Class 4	23 (69.7%)	10 (30.3%)	0 (0.0%)	33 (100.0%)		
Class 5	7 (50.0%)	7 (50.0%)	0 (0.0%)	14 (100.0%)		
LIVING ARRANGEMENT						
With spouse	80 (74.8%)	27 (25.2%)	0 (0.0%)	107 (1000%)	4.296	0.134
without spouse	13 (65.0%)	6 (30.0%)	1 (5.0%)	20 (100.0%)		
PHYSICAL ACTIVITY						
Sedentary	20 (87.0%)	3 (13.0%)	0 (0.0%)	23 (100.0%)	5.578	0.246
Moderate	62 (72.9%)	22 (25.9%)	1(1.2%)	85 (100.0%)		
Heavy	11(57.9%)	8 (42.1%)	0 (0.0%)	19 (100.0%)		
POSTMENOPAUSAL STAGE						
≤7 Years	42 (61.8%)	25 (36.8%)	1 (1.5%)	68 (100.0%)	10.083	0.002***
> 7 Years	51 (86.4%)	8 (13.6%)	0 (0.0%)	59 (100.0%)		

***Statistically significant at 95% level of confidence.

Table 3 shows the association between quality of life (QOL) and sociodemographic variables. A statistically significant association was observed between QOL and education level ($p = 0.006$), indicating that women with higher educational status tended to have better QOL. Similarly, socioeconomic status based on the modified B.G. Prasad scale showed a significant association with QOL ($p = 0.003$), with women in higher socioeconomic classes demonstrating better QOL. Additionally, postmenopausal stage was found to be significantly associated with QOL ($p = 0.002$), as women who were more than seven years postmenopausal had a better quality of life than those within seven years of menopause.

Conversely, no significant associations were found between QOL and age group, type of family, employment status, living arrangement, or physical activity level, indicating that these variables did not significantly influence the quality of life among the study participants.

DISCUSSION

In our study of postmenopausal women in a tertiary care centre, we found that sociodemographic factors such as education, socioeconomic status, and duration since menopause were significantly associated with quality of life (QOL). Specifically, women who were illiterate had markedly poorer QOL (with 36.4% falling into the “poor” category among the illiterate group) compared to those with higher levels of education ($p = 0.006$). Socio-economic status was also strongly associated ($p = 0.003$) — women in the highest class (Class 1) showed very high “good QOL” proportions (~96.3%) compared to lower classes. Furthermore, women >7 years postmenopause had significantly better QOL (86.4% good QOL) compared to ≤7 years (61.8% good QOL), $p = 0.002$. These findings are in line with the study conducted among urban women in Hyderabad, India, where Yerra et al^[5] reported that lack of formal education and lower awareness were associated with higher symptom burden and poorer QOL, particularly in the vasomotor and physical domains. The Hyderabad

study also reported that the physical domain contributed the highest mean MENQOL score (14.89 ± 11.85), followed by vasomotor and psychosocial domains, which is consistent with our study where women reported more disturbances in physical and vasomotor aspects compared to psychosocial and sexual domains. Furthermore, in the Hyderabad study, duration since menopause was a significant factor, with women in the initial years (<5 years) experiencing more vasomotor discomfort. This aligns with our observation that women ≤ 7 years post-menopause experienced poorer QOL compared to those >7 years post-menopause, suggesting that symptom severity may decline over time due to physiological adaptation or improved coping mechanisms.

Similarly our findings align with Sheereen and Kadarkar (2022)^[7] in rural Western Maharashtra, who reported that lower educational status is linked to greater severity of menopausal symptoms and poorer QOL. Education likely enhances awareness, coping strategies, and health-seeking behavior, improving overall well-being during menopause.

Comparing with the Kochi study^[4], the authors found that the mean total MENQOL score was 112.47 ± 28.80 , the highest burden being in the physical domain (62.05 ± 17.82) followed by psychosocial (31.01 ± 9.59), vasomotor (12.59 ± 6.58) and sexual (6.82 ± 1.91) domains. They also reported that educational status and socioeconomic status were highly significantly associated with QOL ($P < 0.01$) and marital status was also significant ($P < 0.05$). Age and occupational status did *not* show significant associations.

In the current study, women in the age group of 45–55 years and 56–60 years showed no statistically significant difference in QOL ($p=1.000$), suggesting that age alone may not be a primary determinant of QOL during menopause. Similar observations were reported by Nisar & Sohoo (2009)^[6], who found that menopausal symptoms were prevalent across various age groups and were more influenced by symptom burden rather than chronological age.

Overall, the findings emphasize that education, socioeconomic well-being, and adaptation time since menopause are major determinants of QOL among postmenopausal women.

CONCLUSION

The present study concludes that quality of life among postmenopausal women is significantly influenced by education level, socioeconomic status, and duration since menopause. Women who were better educated, financially stable, and more than seven years post-menopause exhibited an improved quality of life. No statistically significant association was noted between QOL and age, employment status, family type, physical activity, or living arrangements. These findings highlight

the need for targeted interventions such as health education programs, socioeconomic support strategies, and counseling services, particularly for women in the early postmenopausal years. Enhancing awareness and empowering women through education and social policies can substantially improve their quality of life.

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